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Herbert Bruderer

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Books

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 2. Auflage 2018

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 3. Auflage 2020

Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer, 3rd edition 2020

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- Bruderer, Herbert [2020c]: Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, Cham, 3rd edition 2020, 2 volumes, 2113 pages, 715 illustrations, 151 tables, translated from the German by John McMinn, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-40974-6>

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